

Pentachalcogenide Dianions in Titanium Complexes

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Pentasulphide and pentaselenide complexes of bis(methylcyclopentadienyl)-titanium(IV) and [(cyclopentadienyl), (methylcyclopentadienyl)]titanium(IV) have been prepared. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, i.r. and ^1H n.m.r. spectroscopy. Molecular weight determination and conductivity measurement indicated these complexes to be monomeric and non-electrolytic in nature. On the basis of ^1H n.m.r. spectra a chair configuration is assigned to TiS_5 or TiSe_5 ring in these complexes.

CHUGH and Smith¹ claimed to have prepared $[\text{Cp}_2\text{TiS}_5]$ type complexes but could not offer the characterization. Ralea and coworkers² prepared $[\text{Cp}_2\text{TiSx}]_n$ (where $x=3$ or 4) from Cp_2TiCl_2 and various chlorosulphides and sodium sulphides. However for the first time Kopf and Block³ established that in all the cases only Cp_2TiS_5 could be isolated. Epstein *et al.*^{4,5} on the basis of X-ray diffraction studies have assigned a chair configuration to TiS_5 ring fragment of $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiS}_5$ complex. Literature survey reveals that there is little work on such complexes and no complexes of the type $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiS}_5$, $[\text{Cp}(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiS}_5$ nor their selenium analogue have been prepared so far. We report herein the isolation and characterization of these complexes. On the basis of ^1H i.m.r. spectra and i.r. spectra a chair configuration is assigned to TiS_5 or TiSe_5 ring in these complexes.

Experimental

Reagents and Techniques :

$(\text{Me.C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ was prepared as described by Chandra *et al.*⁶ by the action of TiCl_4 on $(\text{Me.C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Cl}$ (I) in 1 : 2 mole ratio in tetrahydrofuran.

$[\text{Cp}(\text{Me.C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ was prepared by the reaction of CpTiCl_3 (21.9g, 0.1 mole) on $(\text{Me.C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Cl}$ (26.9 g, 0.1 mole) in THF.⁷

Yellow ammonium sulphide was prepared by passing H_2S through a suspension of powdered sulphur in aqueous ammonia till it assumed intense yellow colour.

Sodium pentaselenide was prepared by mixing freshly cut sodium metal (1.150 g, 0.05 mole) with pure selenium metal (9.75 g, 0.125 mole). The reaction mixture was fused on a low flame in a large boiling tube under nitrogen atmosphere. The fused

mass was extracted with deaerated water and the filtrate as such was used.

All the organic solvents used were prepurified and well dried.

Preparation of the Complexes :

A. Preparation of pentasulphides of $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{Ti(IV)}$ and $[\text{Cp}(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{Ti(IV)}$

(i) Preparation of $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiS}_5$

A concentrated aqueous solution was prepared by refluxing for 45 minutes $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (2.77 g, 0.01 mole) in 50 cm³ water to which hydrochloric acid was already added to maintain the pH (1.2-2). The clear dark coloured solution was deaerated by passing N_2 gas. Yellow ammonium sulphide solution was also deaerated and was added slowly to the deaerated solution of $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ under nitrogen. The precipitate was obtained which was extracted in 5×10 cm³ portions of dichloromethane. The combined extract was dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 and filtered. From the filtrate the solvent was distilled off *in vacuo*. The residue left was recrystallized from 1 : 1 THF and petroleum ether, the yield of the orange red $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiS}_5$ was >50%.

Other complexes, $[\text{Cp}(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiS}_5$, $[\text{Cp}(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiSe}_5$ and $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiSe}_5$ were prepared in >50% yield, by the same method using, $[\text{Cp}(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ or $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ and yellow ammonium sulphide or sodium pentaselenide.

Physical measurements :

The i.r. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 621 grating spectrophotometer in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ whereas ^1H n.m.r. spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 spectrometer at ~30°

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA FOR PENTASULPHIDE AND PENTASELENIDE COMPLEXES

Complex	Molar conductivity ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Concentration mM	Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)	% Found (Calcd.)			Melting point and colour
				C	H	Ti	
(MeC ₅ H ₄) ₂ TiS ₅	.68	0.5	381 (366)	40.0 (39.8)	3.7 (3.8)	13.2 (13.1)	200° (d) orange red
[Cp ₂ (MeC ₅ H ₄)]TiS ₅	.65	0.5	365 (362)	37.7 (37.5)	3.2 (3.4)	14.9 (13.6)	260° (d) orange red
(MeC ₅ H ₄) ₂ TiSe ₅	.56	0.5	616 (601)	24.2 (23.96)	2.2 (2.3)	8.1 (7.95)	decomposes about 350° dark purple
[Cp ₂ (MeC ₅ H ₄)]TiSe ₅	.51	0.5	599 (587)	22.1 (22.7)	1.9 (2.06)	7.9 (8.2)	280° (d) dark purple

using TMS as an internal standard at a sweep width of 500 Hz.

Carbon and hydrogen were estimated micro-analytically whereas titanium metal was estimated as TiO₂ gravimetrically. The conductivities of the complexes were determined in nitrobenzene using a Beckman RC-18A conductivity bridge. The molecular weights of the complexes were determined ebullioscopically in benzene.

Results and Discussion

The pentasulphides and selenides of (MeC₅H₄)₂-Ti(IV) and [Cp₂(MeC₅H₄)]Ti(IV) have been prepared by the reaction of (MeC₅H₄)₂TiCl₂ or [Cp₂(MeC₅H₄)]TiCl₂ on yellow ammonium sulphide or sodium pentaselenide in aqueous medium as follows:

The pentasulphide complexes are orange red whereas selenide complexes are dark purple in colour. The pentasulphide complexes have moderate solubility in CS₂, C₆H₆, CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃ and THF whereas selenide complexes are relatively less soluble. All the complexes are thermally stable below their melting points. These complexes hydrolyse very slowly in air whereas their solutions are hydrolysed relatively rapidly. Molecular weight determination in benzene and conductivity measurement in nitrobenzene indicate these to be monomers and non-electrolytes. Physical data for these complexes are given in Table 1.

I. R. spectra :

Infrared and far infrared spectral analysis is of very much use in the characterization of these complexes. The cyclopentadienyl and methylcyclopentadienyl rings are identified by i.r. bands at

~3100 cm⁻¹ due to C-H ring stretching, at ~1440 cm⁻¹ due to C-C asymmetric ring breathing, at ~1030 cm⁻¹ due to C-H in plane bending, at ~825 cm⁻¹ due to C-H out of plane bending. The C-H stretching vibrations due to -CH₃ group of CH₃C₅H₄ appears at ~2900 cm⁻¹. The bands in the spectra of pentasulphides appearing at 510 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to Ti-S bond stretching whereas in pentaselenides the bands appearing at 500 cm⁻¹ are due to Ti-Se bond stretching.

N.M.R. spectra :

The ¹H n.m.r. spectra of pentasulphide or pentaselenide derivatives of (MeC₅H₄)₂Ti(IV) show two types of resonances (i) one due to MeC₅H₄ ring protons appearing in the form of two multiplets at -369 Hz and -360 Hz for pentasulphide and at -371 Hz, and -363 Hz for selenide complex, (ii) the other resonance is due to protons of -CH₃ groups of CH₃C₅H₄ rings appearing in the form of two sharp signals at -135 Hz and -119 Hz for pentasulphide and at -130 Hz and -115 Hz for pentaselenide complex.

The ¹H n.m.r. spectra of [Cp₂(MeC₅H₄)]TiS₅ shows three resonances (i) due to Cp ring protons appearing at -378 Hz, (ii) due to CH₃C₅H₄ ring protons appearing in the form of a multiplet at -366.5 Hz, (iii) due to methyl protons of CH₃C₅H₄ ring appearing at -133 Hz. The ¹H n.m.r. spectra for [Cp₂(MeC₅H₄)]TiSe₅ could not be recorded due to its very poor solubility in CdCl₂.

The ¹H n.m.r. spectra of (MeC₅H₄)₂TiS₅ or (MeC₅H₄)₂TiSe₅, are similar to that of Cp₂TiS₅ which shows two signals due to cyclopentadienyl rings at ~30°, though at elevated temperature (120°) only one peak is found owing to the rapid conformational change⁶.

The ¹H n.m.r. of these complexes like that of Cp₂TiS₅ can be explained only if a chair configuration is assigned to TiS₅ or TiSe₅ ring fragment which results in an asymmetric disposition of the sulphurs with respect to the two methylcyclopentadienyl rings thus making the PMR of the two

Fig. 1. Structure of $(\text{MeC}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiS}_5$, representing chair configuration of TiS_5 ring.

MeC_5H_4 rings non-equivalence and appearing in the form of two multiplets. Since the chair configuration of TiS_5 or TiSe_5 ring fragment results in the non-equivalence of two MeC_5H_4 rings therefore protons of $-\text{CH}_3$ group of each MeC_5H_4 ring give rise to a separate PMR signal. Thus two signals are obtained for $-\text{CH}_3$ groups resonance.

Thus considering the ^1H n.m.f. spectra of these complexes, a chair configuration is assigned to TiS_5

or TiSe_5 ring fragment of these complexes as shown in the Fig. 1.

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